

Table S2.

	Forward	Reverse	Amplicon size (pb)
<i>TMEM56</i>			
Rat	agcaccgagaagaagatcga	aggtagcctgaagcagtcga	173
Ferret	tggacaccaacaccaaactg	aagccaaccaccaaagaa	191
Human	tgccattctttggtggtg	catacagggacgcacaatga	214
Reference Genes			
<i>Gdi</i> (for rat)	ccgcacaaggcaaatacatc	gactctctgaaccgtcatcaa	159
<i>Lrp10</i> (for rat)	tcccctttctctcctcctc	ttaccgtctgttccttgctg	198
<i>Mettl2b</i> (for ferret)	ggtcgtccagacaagatgc	ccgtcccctctcacatagaa	162
<i>RPLP0</i> (for human)	acaaccagctctggagaaa	tgccctggagatttagtg	240